

MANAGEMENT OF STUDENT CHARACTER EDUCATION THROUGH PASKIBRA EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES AT SMA PLUS PGRI CIBINONG

EVA DIANAWATI WASLIMAN

Nusantara Islamic University Bandung, Jl. Soekarno Hatta No. 530, Sekejati, Kec. Buah batu , Bandung City. Email: evadianawatiwasliman@uninus.ac.id

RIA RESTU RAMADHANTY

Nusantara Islamic University Bandung, Jl. Soekarno Hatta No. 530, Sekejati, Kec. Buah batu , Bandung City. Email: resturamadhanty@uninus.ac.id

YENI SUHAENI

Nusantara Islamic University Bandung, Jl. Soekarno Hatta No. 530, Sekejati, Kec. Buah batu , Bandung City. Email: yenisuhaeni@uninus.ac.id

Abstract

The aim of this research is to find out and provide an overview of student character education management through extracurricular activities. The method used in this research is qualitative research with data collection techniques through observation, interviews and documentary studies. The management process consists of planning, organizing, implementing and monitoring. The research results show that there is still a lack of facilities to be used optimally, there are obstacles due to rainy weather and coupled with a lack of support from parents. In fact, in building the character of students, it is hoped that students will be able to learn independently, be disciplined over time, be honest in every action they take and be responsible. Training and educating students makes them become leaders for the nation and state. The implementation of the formation of students may be studied in the classroom, but its implementation can only be supported by extracurricular activities which are expected as the Principal of the School who always hold meetings every 6 months to evaluate students, especially in these extracurricular activities.

Keywords : Manajemen, Character Education; Paskibra Extracurricular.

A. INTRODUCTION

In the world of education, it is known that there are two activities that are quite elementary, namely intracurricular and extracurricular activities (Depag RI, 2004: 4). Where it is mentioned that education can be obtained from activities in the classroom which means the learning process by providing learning material from the teacher to students. As for extracurricular activities, they are activities that have nothing to do with the subject matter and learning process activities are not carried out in the classroom.

Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System Article 3 states that national education functions to develop the ability and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to educate the nation's life, with the aim of developing the potential of students to become human beings who believe and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and be a democratic and responsible citizen. Extracurricular activities are activities in the

self-development of students in character building, when students are in a community environment and cannot be obtained when in the learning process in class.

The purpose of extracurricular activities is to gain additional knowledge, skills and insights and help shape the character of students according to their respective interests and talents. In extracurricular activities, there are several benefits that are useful for character building, namely,

- (1) Making learners active, extracurricular activities require learners to be actively involved. They must participate, collaborate with friends, follow directions, and contribute to group or team goals. This helps train critical thinking, creativity, and leadership skills.
- (2) Teaching teamwork, Learners learn to interact with their peers in different contexts than the classroom. They learn about cooperation, communication, conflict, and how to work in groups. This enriches their social experience.
- (3) Channeling energy and creativity The freedom to express oneself and participate in activities that spark imagination and creativity is an important aspect of many extracurricular activities, such as art, music, and theater. It helps learners learn to think outside the box, create creative solutions, and hone critical thinking skills.
- (4) Extracurricular activities can help reduce stress levels in learners. When they engage in activities they enjoy, endorphins that stimulate feelings of happiness can be released, reducing the stress and tension they may experience in daily life.
- (5) In extracurricular activities, learners will have responsibilities, deadlines, and schedules that they must meet. This creates an opportunity to develop critical time management skills. They learn how to plan, organize, and execute their tasks efficiently.

Effective character education management must be integrated in school management, particularly in school-based management approaches. This is because character education is not just about what is taught to students, but also about how the school as a whole creates an environment that supports positive character development. In other words, character education in schools is also closely related to school management (Agus Wibowo, 2013). Character education is plus ethics education, which involves aspects of knowledge (cognitive), feelings (feeling), and action (action). Without these three aspects, character education will not be effective, so what is needed in character education is not enough with knowledge and then take actions that are in accordance with knowledge alone. This is because character education is closely related to values and norms. Therefore, it must also involve feelings (Akhmad Muhaimin Azzet, 2011).

The application carried out in the development of student character cannot be equated with the development of students when in the classroom, one example is paskibra extracurricular activities. Extracurricular activities like Paskibra are excellent examples of how character development can take place outside of the classroom environment. Here are some reasons why extracurricular activities, such as Paskibra, are important in the

character development of learners because they provide students with leadership experience, teamwork, discipline and rigor, independence, adherence to values and protocols, patriotism and nationality and valuable life experience. Elly Sri Melinda (2013: 2) suggests that activeness in participating in extracurriculars affects discipline, courage, respect for others, care for the environment, love of nature and independence. In line with the scout extracurricular education process that shapes students to be independent, disciplined, and independent in mutual relationships between humans (Team DAP, 2012: 39).

According to the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia No. 23 of 2015 concerning the Growth of Ethics (PBP) Article 1 explains that the growth of ethics is an activity to habituate positive attitudes and behaviors in schools starting from the first day at school, the orientation period for new students to approach junior high school, high school, and vocational high school until school graduation. Forming a nation that is tough, competitive, morally tolerant, cooperative, patriotic, dynamically developing, science-oriented, science-oriented, science-oriented and technology-oriented, all imbued with Faith and Piety to God based on Pancasila, that is the goal in character education (Kemendiknas, 2011) (Wulandari and Kristiawan, 2017) (Kristiawan et al, 2017) (Sayer et al, 2018) (Lian et al, 2018).

This research is expected to provide a deep understanding of how character education management is implemented through extracurricular activities, especially in the context of Paskibra extracurricular activities. This study aims to understand how schools implement character values such as discipline, cooperation, obedience, and leadership through paskibra extracurricular activities. It covers the way character education is applied in the context of the daily practice of the activity. The research location is SMA PLUS PGRI Cibinong, which has its complete address at Jl. Golf, RT.03 / RW.07, Ciriung, Cibinong District, Bogor Regency, West Java.

B. METHOD

Researchers use qualitative methods. Data collection techniques use observation, interviews and documentation studies. The study took samples from principals and teachers at SMA PLUS PGRI Cibinong. Research activities will be carried out March - April 2023. The results of the study are used as research data. The instrument used is in the form of direct interviews by the Principal and Teachers. As for the source of the data, it cannot be directly obtained from archives, but data from schools given to researchers.

Interview is a tool used to find information in accordance with the object studied with a small number of respondents (Sugiyono 2016). Data collection techniques by providing questions directly related to the character management of learners in extracurricular activities.

There are several indicators of the question instrument, including: (1) what is meant by the character of students? (2) How to apply character building to extracurricular paskibra? (3) Is the character building of students easy? (4) What about the supporting factors and obstacle factors after the formation of the character?

The analysis that researchers use, namely data analysis, is a process where the data of the results studied has all been collected (Sugiyono 2016). Researchers collect their observations by making observations in the school field, following activities taught by trainers to students and giving several questions to principals, teachers and trainers whose results from these interviews can be analyzed by researchers.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of research at SMA Plus PGRI Cibinong, Principals, Teachers, Trainers and Students showed mutual discipline. Through the process of character building, students are expected to be able to appropriately train habits or change into good habits. The research location is located at Jl. Golf, RT.03/RW.07, Ciriung, Cibinong District, Bogor Regency, West Java 16918. On March 2, 2023, for the first time, researchers conducted research by coming to the school, with prior permission from the Principal.

A coordination meeting was held between the Principal and the teachers to discuss the implementation plan of Paskibra extracurricular activities. The discussion involved various aspects, including the extracurricular activities themselves, the budget needed for school infrastructure, and integration with the school curriculum. For example, in the context of the formation of extracurricular Paskibra, it should be noted that a policeman from the Cibinong Police Station will be the main instructor who will provide direct training to participants. In this case, the Principal plans to make additional contributions in the form of dues to the learners. The purpose of the presence of a police officer as an instructor is not only limited to physical training such as walking or standing upright, but also to the formation of discipline and character in line with the school's vision and mission in character education.

Planning can be said to be a process of preparation of various activities carried out, planning is related to a series of actions or activities that will be carried out to achieve goals in the future (Sudjana, 2004: 58). The planning program that has been made has a structured nature and is part of the evaluation effort in building the character of students that have been planned. This program is designed by considering the Basic Framework of the 2013 Curriculum as a guideline in the development of character education. By running a planning program that is structured and integrated with the 2013 Curriculum, schools or educational organizations can be more effective in carrying out student character building evaluations and ensuring that character education takes place in accordance with the desired goals.

Furthermore, in organizing the management of Paskibra's extracurricular activities, there are several key roles involving the Coach, Advisory Board, Coach, Chairman, Vice Chairman, and Treasurer. The formation of this organization involves a rigorous selection process to ensure that each individual in the role has the appropriate competencies and qualifications.

The implementation of character education is realized through various activities, such as orientation, inter-school competitions, and Paskibra competitions between individuals from various schools. These activities are designed to strengthen the character values

and skills needed in raising the flag, which will generally be used in commemorating Independence Day at the subdistrict, kelurahan, and provincial levels. In Paskibra activities, there are various materials taught to participants. These include aspects such as health, discipline, marching formation, flag-raising and lowering techniques, as well as the cultivation of nationalist values. This Paskibra extracurricular activity is routinely carried out every Thursday, after the learning process is complete.

Furthermore, related to monitoring the character of students, this monitoring process is carried out directly by a number of parties, including the Principal, Vice Principal, Extracurricular Coach, and Teacher. This monitoring aims to ensure that the planning program that has been prepared or updated every 6 months has development and improvement in student character building. The monitoring process is carried out through a motivational approach to learners. In addition, this approach also aims to measure the achievement of learners in terms of their achievement.

This monitoring is also a means to improve the implementation of learning programs that focus on character education. In situations where there is a deficiency or inconsistency with character-building principles, the Principal will not hesitate to provide appropriate reprimands or corrective actions. The goal is to ensure that students' character building efforts run in accordance with the plans and standards set by the school.

Wahjosumidjo (2007: 205) suggests that the main purpose of supervision is "in the context of coaching, developing, serving, improving quality, and protecting the school concerned." In this context, supervision has a dual purpose, namely to monitor the development of each learner and to further develop extracurricular activities in each school. This monitoring is not only limited to character building, but also includes the active presence of learners in participating in extracurricular activities. Thus, supervision not only focuses on character-building aspects, but also measures the involvement of learners in extracurricular activities, which are integral to their comprehensive development. The main purpose of supervision is to ensure that the education and development of students runs in accordance with established standards and plans.

There are two factors in the application of character education. The first is a supporting factor and the second is an inhibiting factor. The most important supporting factor is funds, because extracurricular activities in each activity are charged every month by the Principal for the continuity or smooth process in extracurricular activities that take place. Then there is support from the coach in teaching the formation of student character to be able to value time, physical formation, apply the values of integrity contained in Pancasila learning that can be realized into everyday life. Such examples are honesty, responsibility, independence, discipline, courage, fairness. As for other supporting factors in the form of school fields for marching exercises. Facilities must be able to meet minimum standards for ongoing learning.

According to Uttoro (2007: 23) factors that affect extracurricular activities, namely environmental conditions, can be divided into two types, namely the surrounding environment and the environment caused by seasonal and climatic factors. Examples for the school environment while maintaining school cleanliness, especially especially the

school field. A clean environment will make comfort, especially students in participating in extracurricular activities and the physical condition of the school is also treated once a year by repainting buildings, caring for plants around the school environment. All of this is done by the Principal in order to support extracurricular activities in building better student character in the future.

Based on the results of the discussion that has been described, it can be concluded that the implementation of student character education through extracurricular Paskibra at SMA PGRI PLUS Cibinong is supported by several key factors. Here are more details on those factors:

1) Places Provided by the School: The School has provided adequate facilities and places for the implementation of Paskibra extracurricular activities. The existence of practice rooms, fields, and other facilities allows students to practice and develop Paskibra skills well.

2) Human Resources: Paskibra's extracurricular success is also supported by quality human resources. The trainers, coaches, and teachers involved in this activity have high competence and dedication to support the formation of student character through Paskibra. They have an important role in providing direction and training to learners.

3) Community Support Around the School: The community environment around the school also plays an important role in the success of the Paskibra extracurricular program. Positive support and active participation from the community support the smooth running of every activity carried out by Paskibra. This creates a conducive climate for the formation of student character through extracurricular activities.

4) School Commitment: Commitment from the school authorities, including the principal and school staff, is very important. They ensure that Paskibra's extracurricular programs receive appropriate support and recognition within the school structure. It also includes adequate budget allocations to support Paskibra activities.

5) Student Participation: The success of the program also depends on the active participation of students in Paskibra extracurricular activities. They must have high motivation and involvement to participate in training, competitions, and other activities related to Paskibra.

Overall, the collaboration between these factors is a strong foundation in the implementation of student character education through extracurricular Paskibra at SMA PGRI PLUS Cibinong. With support from schools, quality human resources, active student participation, and positive community support, this program is able to achieve its goals in shaping student character.

Factors that affect extracurricular activities, namely environmental conditions, can be divided into two. According to Uttoro (2007: 23) factors that affect extracurricular activities, namely environmental conditions, can be divided into two types, namely the surrounding environment and the environment caused by seasonal and climatic factors.

The factors that hinder the implementation of character education at PGRI Plus High School include:

1) Weather or Climate Change: When entering the rainy season, many extracurricular activities that rely on outdoor activities become hampered. Activities such as Paskibra exercises that are generally done outdoors become less efficient or even have to be postponed. Bad weather conditions can endanger the safety of students and disrupt the smooth running of activities.

2) Limited Classrooms: During the rainy season, extracurricular activities that are usually done outdoors need to be moved into the classroom. This can reduce the effectiveness of activities due to limited physical space in the classroom and restrictions on student movement.

3) Competition Facilities: School field facilities, such as sports fields, are often used by some extracurriculars that require outdoor space. This creates competition for the use of facilities, as you mentioned with the example of extracurricular marching bands. Dividing the field into two parts may be a solution, but it can reduce maximization of facility use and affect the quality of training.

4) Sound Disturbances: Sounds from other extracurricular activities, such as music from extracurricular marching bands, can interfere with the focus of students who are undergoing Paskibra training. This can interfere with communication and instruction during exercises, which is important for student character building.

Another inhibiting factor comes from parents who have not been open-minded about paskibra activities in which there is character education. Based on Permendikbud No. 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education, its implementation for extracurricular activities is a strengthening of character values in order to optimally expand the potential, talents, interests, stability, personality, cooperation and independence of students. Similarly, parents who always control their children hard and feel that this extracurricular activity of paskibra is a waste of time and not useful. Because parents' thoughts only focus on exact lessons or focus on grades to the next level, such as college. Where the support from some parents is not optimal so that there are students who are afraid so they leave the scout extracurricular so that the potential that exists in students is not optimally developed. To overcome these obstacles, it is necessary to do creative thinking and good management. This may include more flexible scheduling, alternative use of facilities where possible, and consideration of environmental factors that may affect extracurricular activities. In the event of sound interference, it may be worth considering solutions such as the use of hearing aids or acoustic isolation for the exercise area. The goal is to ensure that character education through extracurriculars continues well, even in unfavorable weather conditions. Overcoming the inhibiting factors of parents who have not fully supported Paskibra extracurricular activities and character education can involve the following steps and approaches: (1) Socialization and Education: Schools can organize special meetings or seminars for parents of students. In this event, schools can explain in detail the benefits of Paskibra activities in the formation of their children's character. Key points, such as leadership development,

discipline, independence, and cooperation, can be emphasized to give parents a better understanding. (2) Involving Parents: Inviting parents to attend some practice sessions or Paskibra activities can be a way to show them firsthand how these activities contribute to the development of their children's character. Parents who see their child's progress for themselves may be more supportive. (3) Open Communication: Schools can create open channels of communication with parents. This allows parents to raise their concerns and gain a deeper understanding of the purpose and benefits of Paskibra activities. Overcoming parental doubts through good dialogue can be an important step. (4) Demonstration of Results: When the opportunity arises, the school can organize events or performances that show parents the achievements and progress that students have made in Paskibra activities. This could include parade performances or performances during Independence Day commemorations. (5) Individual Approach: Some students may have more difficulty convincing their parents. In these cases, an individualized approach by teachers or school staff can help. Teachers can talk to parents privately to explain the positive impact they have seen on their children through participation in Paskibra. (6) School Commitment: Schools must demonstrate a strong commitment to character education through extracurricular activities. This includes periodic assessments of students' character development during their time involved in Paskibra. Concrete data and evidence can be used to convince parents of the benefits of these activities.

With a careful approach and effective communication, schools can overcome obstacles caused by parental views that have not fully supported Paskibra activities and character education. Building understanding and support from parents is an important step in running an extracurricular program successfully.

D. CONCLUDING

Based on the results of research and data analysis conducted by researchers at SMA PLUS PGRI Cibinong, it can be concluded that:

- 1) Character Education Planning through Paskibra Extracurricular Activities:** Character education planning through Paskibra extracurricular activities includes meetings that discuss planning facilities and infrastructure, curriculum, and financing.
- 2) Organizing Character Education through Paskibra Extracurricular Activities:** Organizing character education through extracurricular activities Paskibra is under the auspices of schools and guided by coaches, such as police who train learners in marching learning.
- 3) Implementation of Character Education through Paskibra Extracurricular Activities:** The implementation of character education through Paskibra extracurricular activities includes annual competition activities and participation in the commemoration of August 17 Independence Day through strict selection.
- 4) Monitoring of Character Education through Paskibra Extracurricular Activities:** Monitoring or supervision is carried out directly by the principal, vice principal, extracurricular coaches, and teachers. It aims to ensure the development and

improvement of planning programs every 6 months in the formation of student character.

- 5) **Supporting Factors in Character Education:** Supporting factors include financial aspects (money), facilities, and external coaches from outside the school. External coaches help shape the character of learners, increase motivation, and strengthen character education.
- 6) **Factors that Hinder the Implementation of Character Education:** Factors that hinder the implementation of character education include weather changes, competition of facilities with other extracurricular activities, and lack of parental support that views extracurricular activities only as a waste of time.

Building character education, especially at the high school level, is a challenging task because it involves students who are in the rebellious soul phase and want freedom. Therefore, it is necessary to provide appropriate developmental training to guide learners so that they achieve progress leading to character building according to the correct guidelines. With these steps, it is hoped that students will become leaders of the nation with integrity in accordance with the desired character education goals.

Daftar Referensi

- 1) <http://repository.unim.ac.id/714/3/3.BAB%20II.pdf> diakses pada tanggal 18 september 2023.
- 2) Departemen Agama RI. 2004. Al-Qur'an dan Terjemahannya. Surabaya: Mekar Surabaya
- 3) Permendikbud Nomor 23 Tahun 2015 Tentang Penumbuhan Budi Pekerti (PBP). 2015. Jakarta: Depdiknas.
- 4) Permendikbud No. 87 Tahun 2017 tentang Penguatan Pendidikan Karakter. 2017. Jakarta : Depdiknas.
- 5) Achmad Maulana dkk.(2004). Kamus Ilmiah Populer. Yogyakarta: Absolut. cet. II,
- 6) Akhmad Muhaimin Azzet.(2011).Urgensi Pendidikan Karakter di Indonesia. Jogjakarta: Ar- Ruzz Media.
- 7) Elly Sri Melinda. (2013). Pendidikan Kepramukaan. Jakarta: Luxima Metro Media
- 8) Sudjana, S. (2004). Manajemen Program Pendidikan (Untuk Pendidikan NonFormal dan Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia). Bandung: Fallah Production.
- 9) Sugiyono. (2016) Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif kualitatif dan kombinasi (Mixed Method). Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 10) Uttoro. (2007). Identifikasi Faktor-Faktor Penghambat Pelaksanaan Ekstrakurikuler Bulutangkis di MAN III Yogyakarta. Skripsi. Yogyakarta: FIK UNY.
- 11) Wahjosumidjo. (2007). Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah (Tinjauan Teoritik dan Permasalahannya). Jakarta: PT raja grafindo persanda.
- 12) Wulandari, Y., & Kristiawan, M. (2017). Strategi Sekolah dalam Penguatan Pendidikan Karakter Bagi Siswa dengan Memaksimalkan Peran Orang Tua. JMKSP (Jurnal Manajemen, Kepemimpinan, dan Supervisi Pendidikan), 2(2)